

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

Work Package WP3
Hybrid grid enabling solutions

Deliverable D3.6
VI and Electromagnetic Actuator for Ultra-fast Operation

Funding Instrument: Innovation Action
Call: H2020-LC-SC3-2020-EC-ES-SCC
Call Topic: LC-SC3-ES-10-2020 - DC – AC/DC hybrid grid for a modular, resilient and high RES share grid development

Project Start: 1 October 2020
Project Duration: 48 months

Beneficiary in Charge: EATON

Document Identifier: doi:[10.5281/zenodo.6102427](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6102427)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	✓
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Deliverable Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	HYPERRIDE
Project Number:	957788
Deliverable Number:	D3.6
Deliverable Full Title:	VI and Electromagnetic Actuator for Ultra-fast Operation
Deliverable Short Title:	MVDCCBActuator
Document Identifier:	HYPERRIDE-D36-MVDCCBActuator-submitted
Beneficiary in Charge:	EATON
Report Version:	v1.3
Contractual Date:	30/09/2024
Report Submission Date:	20/11/2024
Dissemination Level:	PU
Nature:	Demonstrator/Prototype
Lead Author(s):	S. Costea (EATON)
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Keywords:	MVDC CB, Medium Voltage DC Grid, Thomson Coil Actuator, European Union (EU), H2020, Project, HYPERRIDE, GA 957788
Status:	_ draft, _ final, _ x submitted

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
25/08/2024	v1.0	S. Costea (EATON)	Draft report
04/09/2024	v1.1	B. Hatsagi (SCiBreak AB), T. Karsten (RWTH Aachen)	Internal review
10/11/2024	v1.2	S. Costea (EATON)	Updated report
20/11/2024	v1.3	G. Jambrich (AIT)	Final report

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Abbreviations

AC	Alternate Current
SCR	Silicon Controlled Rectifiers
FEM	Finite Element Modeling
IO	Input/Output
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
MVDC	Medium Voltage Direct Current
FET	Field Effect Transistor
DC	Direct Current
IGBT	Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor
TCA	Thomson Coil Actuator

Executive Summary

The concept proposed by Eaton in HYPERRIDE for the 14 kV Direct Current (DC) hybrid circuit breaker is integrating a vacuum interrupter in a newly designed actuation system (including control and drive) and a current detection and triggering system. The actuation function was implemented using a TCA (and the electronic driver), in a 3-coil concept for fast opening of the vacuum interrupter, and one coil for closing. The basic functional principles of the mechanical design of the actuator were analysed in a basic Finite Element Modeling (FEM) simulation and the electrical design of the driver was validated in a SPICE modelling and simulation. The electronic control and driver circuit was tested in a separate set-up, before being integrated in the complete actuator system. The actuator system was tested and the results were analysed for consistency and reliability.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This report is describing the design and testing of the actuator block (in task 3.6 of the HYPERRIDE project) which will be used for the 14 kV DC hybrid circuit breaker (with the concept developed in task 3.8 of HYPERRIDE).

1.2 Structure of the Document

The report starts with a presentation of the main actuation concepts proposed for hybrid circuit breakers in literature, in Section 2. In Section 3, the selected actuation concept is presented, including general mechanical description, modelling and simulation results, prototype design and manufacturing. The electronic control and drive sub-system is presented in Section 4, starting with the electrical diagram and simulation, and continuing with electronic board manufacturing and testing. The testing of the full actuation system is presented in Section 5, including laboratory test set-up description (sub-section 5.1), and the test results (sub-section 5.2). The conclusions and proposal for the next steps are presented in Section 6.

2 Hybrid circuit breaker actuation

The protection challenges of DC power systems have been discussed in literature (Pei et al., 2016) and previous HYPERRIDE reports (Norrnga et al., 2022), (Hatsagi, Nee, Norrga, & Modeer, 2021), (Hatsagi, Bergquist, Nee, Granath, & Modeer, 2023).

As shown in these papers, if a classical mechanical interrupter is used in DC power systems, the breaking of the main current will trigger an arc discharge between the separating contacts. Because in DC power systems there is no natural zero crossing of the main current, the arc it is not quenched naturally, and new measures are needed. In addition, the impedance of the DC cables is much lower ($R = 0.1 - 0.5 \Omega/km$ and $L = 0.3 - 0.6 mH/km$) (Wang, Ming, & Liang, 2019)(Hetzenecker, 2023) than for the Alternate Current (AC) power lines (with impedance between 0.1 and $2 \Omega/km$ (Wang et al., 2019)). Therefore, very fast current increases occur in case of short circuit. Another challenge is added in case of a short circuit in a DC power system, because the DC link capacitors of the power converters will discharge in the first $10 \mu s$, generating a current spike that can damage the equipment.

To prevent dangerous situations, the protection devices in a DC system need to act fast, and to implement features to avoid arc discharge. Considering these issues, CIGRE TB 683, Section 2.2 recommends the following features for DC circuit breakers:

- Fast current interruption capability (in a few milliseconds),
- Creation of a local DC current zero,
- Insertion of a counter-voltage,
- Dissipation of the inductive energy stored in the network.

The main stages of the current interruption operation in a DC circuit breaker, as defined by CIGRE TB683, are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Current evolution during the circuit breaker operation (CIGRE TB683).

The technology that offers advantages in many situations and achieves the fastest operation for this purpose is the solid-state circuit breaker, which uses only semiconductor devices in the main current conduction path (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Solid state circuit breaker diagram (Tapia, Baraia-Etxaburu, Valera, Sanchez-Ruiz, & Abad, 2019).

However, although this solution is fast and fully controllable, the device (usually Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor (IGBT)) is always in the current path, so the non-negligible series resistance will cause power losses even during normal operation.

Figure 3: Hybrid circuit breaker diagram (Tapia et al., 2019).

For minimizing the losses during normal operation, one can employ the hybrid circuit breaker, which uses a mechanical switch to assure a low resistance in the main current path during normal operation.

The system has lower losses in normal operation than the solid-state circuit breaker, but the overall switching time is longer, because of the slow mechanical switch. As the short circuit current can reach dangerous levels very quickly, an additional device is recommended for limiting the rate at which the current increases. Usually, this function is implemented by an air-core inductor, with calculated inductance for the targeted current slope. The inductor selection is also considering other factors, such as the circuit topology, and the distance to the fault. In addition, the hybrid circuit breaker has to limit the duration of the arc discharge that would appear when opening the mechanical switch. The arc is quenched when the main current through the switch is zero. Therefore, the hybrid circuit breaker is inducing a zero-crossing of the main current (passing through the mechanical switch), using a semiconductor circuit (Figure 3).

As mentioned before, the switching speed of mechanical switches is several orders of magnitude slower compared to solid-state breakers (Xu, Damle, & Graber, 2019). For this reason, mechanical switches need to be driven by ultrafast actuators. In order to enable the breaking of the current before it reaches dangerous levels and to limit the amount of energy to be absorbed by semiconductor devices and surge arresters.

The common actuators proposed for hybrid circuit breakers are based on electromagnetic force. There are several examples, like moving coil actuators (D. Vilchis-Rodriguez, Shuttleworth, & Barnes, 2016), doubled-sided coil actuators (Bissal, Magnusson, & Engdahl, 2012), induction switch, series coil switch (Puumala & Kettunen, 2015) and railgun actuator (Challita & Uva, 2014).

The TCA Thomson coil actuator is the most popular mechanism in the literature for ultrafast switching (Al-Dweikat et al., 2022). It employs electromagnetic repulsion force to separate contacts, achieving opening times, shown as fault neutralization time in Figure 1 (defined as the time needed for reaching a contact separation that is large enough to prevent arc re-ignition) as short as hundreds of microseconds.

3 Thomson Coil Actuator (TCA) - Design

3.1 Concept Description

Electromagnetic repulsion mechanisms-based TCA systems could be categorised into two types (Al-Dweikat et al., 2022), depending on the driving principle:

1. coil–coil repulsion mechanism (series coils' configuration),
2. coil–disc repulsion mechanism (induction configuration).

The coil-coil principle (shown in Figure 4 a)), is using the repulsion force between two magnetic fields of opposite directions. In this implementation, two coils are placed coaxially, in a serial electrical connection, and a current pulse is driven through them. As the coils are wound in opposite directions, the magnetic fields will oppose each other and the force will be repulsive. If the coils are connected in a series circuit, a single driving system can be used, as in Figure 4 a), where C is a storage capacitor, U_c is the charging voltage, T is the thyristor, and F is the electromagnetic repulsion force. While the repulsion force is significant, there are drawbacks of the principle, such as the mechanical complexity given by a moving coil and the total inductance of the system (two coils in series), which will affect the current pulse timing (thus affecting the actuation speed).

Figure 4: TCA principles.

The coil-disk mechanism (shown in Figure 4 b)), is using a different physical principle. Instead of a second coil, an aluminum disk is used. The driving circuit and the coil-metal disk system are shown in Figure 4 b). The coil is energized with a current pulse generated by discharging the pre-charged capacitor. The pulse current induces a variable magnetic field, which, in turn, induces eddy currents in the metal disk. These currents are creating a second magnetic field, which is opposing the magnetic field of the coil, and a strong repulsive force between the coil and the metallic disk is developed. Employing such a physical principle in switching is realised by mechanically connecting the moving element (metal disk or second coil) to the mechanical switch for contact separation, moving the contact through a transmission rod (as in Figure 4 b)). A TCA system can generate high forces and high moving speeds, assuring fast contact separation of the mechanical switch in the circuit breaker. On the down side, the high speed creates challenges in stopping safely the contact in the open position (without a mechanical shock - "hammer blow" - which can damage the structure). Damping mechanisms are usually proposed, including passive (mechanical) damping or active damping (D. S. Vilchis-Rodriguez, Shuttleworth, Smith, & Barnes, 2019). In the HIPERRIDE concept for the 14 kV DC circuit breaker, both solutions are used, with the closing coil being used for the active damping. After the first opening impulse applied on the opening coils, as the aluminum disks are moving towards the open position (close to the closing coil), the closing coil, is briefly

energised, creating a repulsive force which dampens the movement.

The TCA devices can be used for various voltage and current ranges (for circuit breakers rated up to 40 kV and currents up to 30 kA (Al-Dweikat et al., 2022)), depending on the capability of the switches that are operated.

Typically, the full TCA system includes a contact opening mechanism, a contact closing mechanism and a lock for the open position (Figure 5). For the HYPERRIDE concept, the targeted Medium Voltage Direct Current (MVDC) circuit breaker has the specifications described in the technical report D3.1 "Requirements on MVDC circuit breakers" ((Norruga et al., 2022)) with an interrupting time (measured from the over-current detection until the contact separation, that does not allow arc reignition) of 2 ms. The proposed implementation included a WL41143 vacuum interrupter, for 1.2 kA operating current, and voltages up to 17.5 kV (Eaton data sheet), with a contact stroke of 10 mm. Therefore, a topology with 3-coil-disk (aluminum disk) system is proposed for the opening mechanism, while the closing mechanism has one coil (with one of the aluminum disks). Although the locking mechanism can be implemented with mechanical blockers, as shown in (Al-Dweikat et al., 2022), in the 14 kV circuit breaker concept the locking system is implemented with a permanent magnet, avoiding mechanical locks with moving parts, which can introduce delays.

Figure 5: Full TCA system.
Modified from (Al-Dweikat et al., 2022)

The 3 disk system allows less strict requirements for the thickness and for the material strength of the moving disk. Also, aluminum is recommended in order to reduce the mass that needs to be set in motion by the actuation force, thus a higher moving speed could be achieved.

3.2 Modelling and Simulation

Figure 6 shows the ANSYS modelling set-up for simulating the moving speed, the force and the contact separation over time, when the actuator is energised. The axi-symmetrical 2-D model

includes the three opening coils (O1 to O3) with three moving aluminum disks (in blue), and a closing coil (C).

Figure 6: ANSYS model set-up.

Figure 7: TCA drive schematic.

As described in the previous section, the mechanical actuation is achieved by applying a controlled current through the coils. A general schematic for the proposed driving circuit is shown in Figure 7. Using this circuit, we simulated the time evolution of the capacitor current, as discharging through the coils (shown in Figure 8). The capacitor is pre-charged from the voltage source V1 using switching transistor Q2, to a voltage level that will enable the movement of the contact at a suitable speed (for fast actuation of the circuit breaker). When the opening operation is triggered, the capacitor will discharge, through SCR1, creating a current pulse through the opening coils O1, O2 and O3 (connected in series). The current through the capacitor

Figure 8: The current through the capacitor, associated with the two coils.

and through the opening coils (forming a resonant LC circuit) will vary in a damped oscillation, with changing direction after the first opening pulse. In Figure 8, it can be seen that the current through the capacitor reaches zero (pink curve), and the control circuitry is switching the contact from the opening coils to the closing coil (SCR1 is blocking, SCR2 and SCR3 are unblocked), for active damping of the opening (shown as the blue curve). For the closing operation, the capacitor has to be charged as shown in Figure 7 (green + and - signs). Because in this implementation the closing operation requires an inverse polarization of the capacitor, compared with the opening operation, an additional step is needed. After charging the capacitor with the same polarity as for opening, the closing operation starts by unblocking SCR4, while the other thyristors are blocked. The capacitor is thus discharged through the additional inductor ("Current limiter" in Figure 7), creating the resonant current which will inverse the capacitor polarity after half period. At this moment, when the voltage on the capacitor will match the green + and - signs in the figure, SCR4 is blocked and SCR2 and SCR3 are unblocked, energising the closing coil, this time for the proper closing operation.

This current pulse will trigger the time profiles of the force, speed and displacement for the moving contact, for 2 ms simulation time, as shown in Figures 9, 10, and 11.

Figure 9: The force created on the moving disk, and transmitted to the contact.

Figure 10: The simulated speed of the moving contact.

Figure 11: The relative displacement of the moving contact during actuation.

3.3 Driver Equivalent Circuit

In a more detailed analysis, the ANSYS simulation shows the current waveform for each inductor and voltage waveform for the 5 mF capacitor (see Figures 12 and 13). Using these waveforms as reference, the inductance parameters have been calculated.

The equivalent circuit for the driving circuit in Figure 7 is shown in Figure 14. This circuit can be used to derive the parameters of one element (inductor or capacitor), assuming that the other element is defined. If we assumed the value of the capacitance known, the inductance parameters can be calculated.

$$-\frac{d^2V(t)}{dt} - \frac{R_{esr}}{L_{tc}} \frac{dV(t)}{dt} - \frac{1}{C_r L_{tc}} V(t) = 0 \quad (1)$$

L_{tc} represents the total coil inductance. By solving the differential Equation 1, capacitor voltage and current values can be computed as expressed by Equation 4 and Equation 5. In these

Figure 12: Opening phase wave forms.

Figure 13: Closing phase wave forms.

Figure 14: Equivalent circuit for calculations.

equations, the resonant angular frequency is given by

$$\omega_n = 1/\sqrt{C_r L_{tc}} \tag{2}$$

and the ratio of resistance over inductance is

$$R/L_{tc} = 2\epsilon\omega_n \tag{3}$$

where ϵ is the damping factor.

$$V(t) = V(0^-)e^{-\epsilon\omega_n t} \times \cos(\omega_n \times \sqrt{1 - \epsilon^2} \times t) \tag{4}$$

$$i(t) = V(0^-) \sqrt{\frac{C_r}{L_{tc}}} e^{-\epsilon \omega_n t} \times \left(\epsilon \times \cos(\omega_n \sqrt{1 - \epsilon^2} \times t) + \sqrt{1 - \epsilon^2} \times \sin(\omega_n \times \sqrt{1 - \epsilon^2} \times t) \right) \quad (5)$$

3.4 Opening Coil Calculation

To calculate the inductance and series resistance of the opening coil, certain parameters can be derived from Figure 12. The required parameters to calculate opening coil parameters are as follows:

- Half period of oscillation: 0.5 ms for opening phase,
- Initial voltage of the capacitor: 900 V at the beginning of the opening phase,
- Capacitor voltage at the end of the half resonant period: -450 V,
- Peak current value: 21.5 kA.

3.4.1 Resistance Calculation

The equivalent resistance of the opening coil can be calculated by considering the electrical energy in the capacitor at different stages. If we take into account that the opening and closing coils are also performing the actuation, we can calculate the coil resistance as the electrical equivalent of all the physical phenomena that are occurring: the thermal dissipation due to the resistance of the conductors, as well as the mechanical energy that is used to move the actuator.

$$E_0 = \frac{1}{2} CV^2 \quad (6)$$

$$E_0 = \frac{1}{2} \times (5 \times 10^{-3} F) \times (900 V)^2 = 2025 J \quad (7)$$

$$E_{500 \mu} = \frac{1}{2} \times (5 \times 10^{-3} F) \times (-450 V)^2 = 506.25 J \quad (8)$$

$$E_{loss} = E_0 - E_{500 \mu} = 1518.75 J \quad (9)$$

where E_{loss} is the energy lost during the first interval of the opening phase.

Therefore, the energy lost and used during first half of the resonant interval is 1518.75 J as seen in Equation 9. Equation 11 can be used to calculate the opening coil equivalent resistance. In this equation:

$$R_{oc} = \frac{E_{loss}}{\left(\frac{I_{ocpk}}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2 \times \frac{T_{oc}}{2}} \quad (10)$$

$$R_{oc} = \frac{1518.75 J}{\left(\frac{21.5 kA}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2 \times \frac{10^{-3} s}{2}} = 13.14 m\Omega \quad (11)$$

- I_{ocpk} is the opening coil peak current value
- T_{oc} is the period of the resonant signal

3.4.2 Inductance Calculation

In order to reduce the duration of transient behaviour during opening operation, the associated RLC circuit should operate close to the critical damping frequency. Therefore, the inductance value L_{oc} can be estimated by assuming that the frequency deviation at opening D_{oc} , described in Equation 12 is at minimum.

$$D_{oc} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{C_r L_{oc}} - \frac{R_{oc}^2}{4L_{oc}^2}} - \omega_{oc} \quad (12)$$

In this equation ω_{oc} is the angular frequency of the opening phase. The minimum for D_{oc} , is reached (using Wolfram Mathematica) for an opening coil inductance of 4.85 μH , using the capacitance value of 5 mF.

3.5 Closing Coil Calculation

The inductance and equivalent resistance (including the mechanical energy spent to close the actuator) of the closing coil were calculated from the parameters of the current waveform in the second phase of the opening operation (Figure 12).

The known parameter values are as follows:

- Capacitor initial voltage is 450 V,
- Capacitor end of operation voltage is 260 V,
- Oscillation peak current value is -5 kA,
- Half period of the oscillation is 1.16 ms and the angular frequency is 2708.24 rad/sec.

3.5.1 Resistance Calculation

As in the case of the first phase of the opening operation, the energy dissipated during half resonant period in the second phase. It is thus possible to obtain the equivalent resistance of the closing coil, with all the energy consuming phenomena included. According to Equation 15 and Equation 16, the equivalent resistance is obtained as 23.25 $m\Omega$.

$$E_0 = \frac{1}{2} \times (5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ F}) \times (450 \text{ V})^2 = 506.25 \text{ J} \quad (13)$$

$$E_{1.16 \text{ m}} = \frac{1}{2} \times (5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ F}) \times (260 \text{ V})^2 = 169 \text{ J} \quad (14)$$

$$E_{cc-loss} = E_0 - E_{1.16 \text{ m}} = 337.25 \text{ J} \quad (15)$$

$$R_{cc} = \frac{E_{cc-loss}}{\left(\frac{I_{cc-pk}}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2 \times \frac{T_{cc}}{2}} R_{cc} = 23.25 \text{ m}\Omega \quad (16)$$

3.5.2 Inductance Calculation

To calculate the closing coil inductance, the same method was used, by searching for the minimum value for the angular frequency deviation D_{cc} in Equation 17. Using a software application (such as Wolfram Mathematica) for reaching the minimum, the L_{cc} value has been obtained as 26.57 μH .

$$D_{cc} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{C_r L_{cc}} - \frac{R_{cc}^2}{4L_{cc}^2}} - \omega_{cc} \quad (17)$$

3.6 Current Limiter Coil Calculation

The parameters of the inductor used as current limiter were calculated from Figure 13, showing the second phase of the closing operation. There are two possible methods to calculate the equivalent resistance:

1. Using the voltage waveform from Figure 13, between from 0 ms and 5 ms,
2. Using the voltage waveform in Figure 13, between 5 ms and 11 ms.

On another hand, the inductance value for the current limiter coil was calculated from the second phase of the closing operation, because the current waveform is available only for this interval.

3.6.1 Resistance Calculation

In the second phase of the closing operation current flows through closing coil and current limiter coil. Therefore, the calculation will determine the total equivalent resistance. In order to obtain the resistance of the current limiter coil, the closing coil resistance (23.25 $m\Omega$ as in Equation 16) will be subtracted from the total resistance.

$$E_0 = \frac{1}{2} \times 5 \times 10^{-3} \times (-900)^2 = 2025 J \quad (18)$$

$$E_{6m} = \frac{1}{2} \times 5 \times 10^{-3} \times 760^2 = 1444 J \quad (19)$$

According to Equations 18 and 19, the energy dissipated during closing operation's second interval is 581 J. The parameters required to calculate the current limiter coil equivalent resistance are as follow:

- Peak current value (I_{ll-pk}) during this interval which is -2.6 kA.
- Time interval to closing operation second phase which is 1.3 ms. And period value (T_{ll-cc}) for this interval is 2.6 ms.

$$R_{II} = \frac{E_{loss}}{\left(\frac{I_{II-pk}}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2 \times \frac{T_{II-cc}}{2}} - R_{cc} \quad (20)$$

After computing Equation 20, the equivalent current limiter coil resistance is obtained as $5.89 \text{ m}\Omega$.

3.6.2 Inductance Calculation

To calculate the inductance of current limiter coil, the same approach will be used as for opening and closing coils. In the following equation there is just one unknown which is L_{II} . And the goal is to find the minimum positive value for D_{III} (angular frequency deviation).

$$D_{III} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{C_r(L_{cc} + L_{II})} - \frac{R_{cc}^2}{4(L_{cc} + L_{II})^2}} - \omega_{II} \quad (21)$$

In Equation 21, $\omega_{II} = 523.6 \text{ rad/s}$ is the angular frequency of the voltage waveform during the second phase of the closing operation. The current limiter inductance value has been obtained as $702.26 \text{ }\mu\text{H}$.

3.6.3 Simulation results

The simulation model has been developed using LTspice, as seen as Figure 15. The calculated inductance parameters have been tuned slightly to fit the simulation curves better in Figures 12 and 13. The simulation time was 25 ms and the critical circuit parameters are as follows:

Parameter	Inductance	Resistance
Opening coil	$4.85 \text{ }\mu\text{H}$	$11.2 \text{ m}\Omega$
Closing Coil	$26.57 \text{ }\mu\text{H}$	$23.26 \text{ m}\Omega$
Current limiter	$702.26 \text{ }\mu\text{H}$	$5.89 \text{ m}\Omega$

The simulation results are shown in Figures 16 and 17. The green trace shows capacitor voltage, the blue trace is showing the opening coil current, pink is the closing coil current, and burgundy is the limiter coil current. Figure 16 shows the opening operation wave forms and Figure 17 shows the closing operation wave forms.

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Figure 15: Simulation circuit.

Figure 16: Opening operation: capacitor voltage and inductor current.

The capacitor current in the first half of the closing operation depends on the specifications of the current limiting inductor. As the purpose of this stage is to obtain a reverse polarity on the capacitor (needed to drive the closing coil actuation), this current value is not used as design parameter.

Figure 17: Closing operation capacitor voltage and inductor current waveforms.

4 Thomson Coil Drive System

The electronic controller unit that triggers the TCA actuation, with the schematic shown in Figure 15, has the block diagram in Figure 18.

The four thyristors Silicon Controlled Rectifiers (SCR) (SCR1 to SCR4)) are controlled by dedicated drivers (UnitB), to enable the charging operation of capacitor Cr (5 mF), through a precharger DC/DC converter that is connected during pre-charging phase using a MOS-FET switch (UNIT D).

Figure 18: System elements for vacuum interrupter driving.

The overall control algorithm is programmed in a micro-controller board (UNIT A), that operates the driver blocks UNIT B and UNIT C, for coordinated operation of the four thyristors and the MOS-FET switch for the pre-charging.

4.1 Controller - Unit A

UNIT A consists of two boards named as main and microcontroller. The main board provides regulated 5V to the isolated DC/DC supplies for driver units, to fiber optic transmitters and receivers, and to the microcontroller board. Interfacing between main board and the microcontroller board is done by 2.54 mm pin-headers.

UNIT A provides thyristor trigger signals to start the opening and closing operations, depending on the command that will come from an external source. For interfacing with an external controller it has 4 digital Input/Output (IO) which are optically isolated. The IO terminals are as follow:

- Opening operation command digital input,
- Closing operation command digital input,
- Error output signal to inform the external controller about hardware problems,

- Status output signal to inform the external controller that the system is currently able to or not to do opening or closing operations.

The controller's properties/capabilities are as follow:

- Provides isolated DC/DC power supplies for gate drives¹,
- Able to monitor DC/DC isolated converters' health²,
- Provides 4 thyristor driving signals³,
- Provides 1 FET driving signal for enabling or disabling the capacitor charger,
- Capacitor voltage monitoring comparator circuit,
- Supplied by 5 V and it has backup energy storage⁴ to deliver power issue information to external controller in case the power is gone,
- The delay of the opening operation is about $3 \mu s$ ⁵.

The micro-controller and main board designs are as seen in Figure 19 and Figure 20. The board generates the signals for the thyristor gate drivers and for the switch between charging source and capacitor bank. The microcontroller board is easily attachable to the main board.

Figure 19: Microcontroller PCB design.

¹5 V to 12 V 2 W converters

²Via optocoupler

³Pulse widths are about $10 \mu s$

⁴Super capacitor, provides power for 20 s

⁵When signal has been received this is the delay of starting of driving sequence

Figure 20: Main board PCB design.

Figure 21: Flowchart of the embedded software.

4.2 Thyristor Driver - Unit B

The schematic of the thyristor driver block was implemented with a ACPL-W349-060E gate driver, as seen in Figure 22 and in Figure 23. The thyristor implementation offers some advantages:

- Short circuit protection through re-settable fuse,
- High frequency immunity implemented by a ferrite-bead,
- High supply voltage protection through 18 V Zener diode,
- Reverse supply protection.

Figure 22: Thyristor driver (UNIT B) schematic.

Figure 23: Thyristor driver (UNIT B) layout.

4.3 FET Driver - Unit C

This is the unit that is responsible to drive the MOS-FET as shown in Figure 24. The design included:

- Short circuit protection through resettable fuse,
- To increase high frequency immunity there is a ferrite-bead,

- High supply voltage protection through 18 V Zener diode,
- Reverse supply protection,
- The gate driver is implemented with 1ED3122MC12HXUMA1.

Figure 24: MOSFET driver (UNIT C) schematic.

The isolated power supply will be provided by controller board therefore there is no isolation between input of the driver and the output.

4.4 High Impedance Switch - Unit D

The DC/DC charger is used in the preparatory step for the TCA operation. During the opening and closing operations, the capacitor (5 mF) is disconnected from the DC/DC charger using a high impedance MOS-FET. The schematic and layout for UNIT D can be seen in Fig-26 and Fig-27.

The design for Unit D board includes the following:

- Snubber components for MOS-FET and for diode. The snubber design depends on the length of the cable used for connections.
- Gate-source high voltage protection using a Zener diode.
- Gate-source capacitance discharge resistor.

Figure 25: MOSFET driver (UNIT C) layout.

- Prepared for heat-sink in case of high power operation.

Figure 26: Switch circuit (UNIT D) schematic.

Figure 27: Switch circuit (UNIT D) layout.

4.5 Experimental Results

Designed and manufactured electronic boards are as in Fig-28 and Fig-29.

Figure 28: UNIT A Main board and controller.

Figure 29: UNIT B, UNIT C, and UNIT D.

The waveforms from Fig-30 to Fig-32 are from opening action. In this test case the capacitor block is charged to 500V and a half sine-wave with 10 kA peak current passes through the

opening coils⁶. In the waveforms, the blue curve is voltage across the capacitors, green is the current measured from the capacitor terminal⁷, orange waveform shows SCR1 trigger signal from the microcontroller dedicated pin, and the pink is drive signal for UNIT D⁸.

Fig-33 and Fig-34 are generated from 750 V charge case of the capacitors and the waveforms are for opening operation. Half sine wave peak value achieved 13.84 kA in this case. In the waveform outputs, the blue one is capacitor voltage, green is the current passing through the capacitors, orange is SCR1 trigger signal from microcontroller side, and the pink is SCR2 trigger signal from the microcontroller dedicated pin. During the opening operation SCR2 is being triggered for slow-down motion by providing repulsive force, by this, it helps to the mechanical damper.

Fig-35 and Fig-36 are generated from 800 V charge case of the capacitors and the waveforms are from opening operation. The peak current was achieved as 14.56 kA. The blue curve is the voltage across the capacitors through out the whole opening operation, the green curve is the current waveform, the orange is SCR1 trigger signal, and the pink is SCR2 trigger signal from the microcontroller's dedicated pin.

Figure 30: 500 V and 10 kA Test Case.

⁶Three coils are connected in series

⁷Current is being measured with a Rogowski probe

⁸high impedance provider between charging source and the capacitors

Figure 31: 500 V and 10 kA Test Case zoom in.

Figure 32: 500 V and 10 kA Test Case zoom in.

Figure 33: 750 V and 13.84 kA Test Case.

Figure 34: 750 V 13.84 kA Test Case zoom in.

Figure 35: 750 V/14.56 kA Test Case.

Figure 36: 750 V/14.56 kA Test Case.

5 Thomson Coil Actuator Prototype

5.1 Prototype Design

The TCA prototype design is shown in the 3D rendering and manufacturing files (see Figure 37). Figure 39 shows the full assembly and a picture of the actual system built for testing.

Figure 37: The 3D design of the TCA prototype.

As the competing objectives of the design were the high actuation speed and the effective damping of the shaft movement, the proposed solution included a mechanical damper, shown on the left side of Figure 37. The damper was designed for an operation in 2 stages, with two bucket shaped inertial masses, which will absorb the energy of the moving shaft. The shaft will hit the first, larger mass, losing most of its energy. This impact will move the larger mass (with significantly lower speed) towards the smaller one, and will transfer the rest of the kinetic energy to it. The smaller mass will also be set in motion, and will move towards a final damping component, with a classical design including a spring and an oil damper.

5.2 Prototype Manufacturing

The prototype was made of steel (the main shaft and the locking disks), Aluminum (for the TCA moving disks), and glass fiber, for the insulating parts (such as coil holders) and for the mechanical structure (the spacers completing the "body") of the actuator. Some of the components designed for the prototype are shown in Figure 38.

Mechanical assembly

Figure 38: Example of components for the TCA prototype.

The actuator structure was assembled using 12 threaded rods as seen in Figure 42. The actuation of the interrupter contact was implemented by mechanically connecting the TCA shaft to the moving contact, while the other contact was fixed to the actuator frame. This assembly can be seen in the bottom part of Figures 39 and 40.

Figure 39: The TCA prototype assembly (3D drawing) and the actual system built for testing.

Figure 40: Full TCA system in the frame.

5.3 Testing set-up

The testing of the actuator system was performed by preparing a computer interface board, which enables sending individual commands to the actuator subsystems from a Python or MATLAB script. Figure 41 shows the testing system set-up.

Figure 41: Testing set-up.

The Python script controls the laboratory equipment and sends the trigger signals, as follows:

- sets the power level of the high voltage power supply (Magna Power TS-3U), then connects briefly to the capacitor bank for a controlled charging current, and disconnects, once the capacitors are charged.
- send the open or close trigger signal to the actuator, through the PC interface.
- capture the position transient measured by the LASER position sensor (optoNCDT 2300 from [Micro-Epsilon](#)).

5.4 Prototype Testing

The basic functional validation of the TCA design was performed by testing with a prototype, in two stages.

In first stage, the prototype was built with only one of the opening coils (see Figure 42) and the operation was tested. As the figure shows, it was found that the Thomson coil will move the Aluminum disk by 6 mm in 5ms, when the coil was energised by a 750 V pre-charging voltage (on capacitor Cr in Figure 15). For the first prototype, the laser position sensor was not available, so the speed and the separation was derived by examining the recording of a high speed camera (10,000 frames per second). In principle, this approach has a high amount of uncertainty, and an automatic image processing algorithm is recommended for repeatable results. In HYPERRIDE we did not pursue this direction, and the dedicated position sensor

Figure 42: The first stage prototype. Displacement at 750 V pre-charge.

was installed to measure the variation of shaft position over time. The results obtained with this sensor are presented in the following sections.

The full prototype, including all three opening coils and aluminum disks, was tested in the set-up described in Figure 41, and the position of the moving contact was monitored with the laser based sensor. Figure 43 shows the detail of the system with the vacuum interrupter, indicating the moving contact and the LASER sensor placement.

Figure 43: The vacuum interrupter contacts and the LASER sensor placement.

The value of the voltage that is used to pre-charge the capacitor bank will determine the force that is created between the opening coils and the aluminum disks, which will directly affect the speed of the moving components of the actuator. The main requirement is a fast movement. In our case, from Deliverable 3.1 "The requirements on MVDC circuit breakers" ((Norrgra et al., 2022)), it was recommended that the current through the vacuum interrupter be interrupted faster than 2 ms. Therefore, the higher the pre-charge voltage, the faster the movement.

However, a fast moving contact is difficult to stop, even with active damping, and a significant bouncing effect will occur. The moving contact will not be locked in the open position and the circuit will be reconnected. For our prototype, a stable opening operation was achieved for a pre-charge voltage of 650 V. An example of the opening operation, as recorded by the LASER position sensor, is shown in Figure 44. The sensor position in figures 44, 45, and 46 has an initial shift of about 5 mm. This was the value measured by the sensor as it was attached in the system, with the contact closed. A calibration step (to bring the measured value to 0), was not considered critical, since the assessment takes into account only the difference between the current position and the initial position.

Figure 44: Moving contact position during opening operation.

In the detail figure it can be seen that the contact moves by about 10 mm in about 2 to 3 ms, corresponding to an average speed of 3-5 m/s. Also, despite the significant bouncing effect, the contact is locked in the open position. This result satisfies the requirement for opening the contact fast enough for the specifications described in (Norrga et al., 2022). Also, similar results were reported in (Chunguang, Jinjin, Ying, Yundong, & Yuchen, 2016), (Zhang et al., 2016) and (Nanxun et al., 2017).

The timing closing of the vacuum interrupter, using the closing coil, is less critical, because it can be performed in controlled set-up. The TCA prototype was tested for a pre-charge voltage of 400 V, which was applied to the closing coil. Position of the moving contact during the closing operation is shown in Figure 45. It can be seen that the closing takes place in about 20 ms (0.5 m/s).

Figure 45: Moving contact position during closing operation.

The longer duration of the closing operation, compared to the opening operation, was used also in previous studies, presented in (Al-Dweikat et al., 2022).

The stability of the opening operation was assessed with repeated measurements. For each measurement, similar to the result in Figure 44, the stroke distance and the timing of the opening was recorded and the 102 validated measurements were analysed statistically using the histogram of three parameters:

- Actuator stroke - it is calculated by calculating the difference between the measured position in the open state and the measured position in the closed state. For a realistic calculation, the average of the sensor readings in the two states is taken into account.
- t_{10-90} - it is the time in which the moving contact moves from the position at 10% of the stroke to the position at 90% of the stroke.
- $t_{7.5}$ - it is the time in which the moving contact moves 7.5mm. From our measurements, it seems that most measurements needed a time close to 2ms to achieve this contact separation.

The calculation of these parameters is shown in Figure 46.

Figure 46: The parameters considered for assessing the consistency of actuator opening operation.

Figure 47: The histogram of the total actuator stroke for 102 measurements.

Figure 47 shows that more than 80% of the measured operations have a stroke between 9.8mm and 10.8mm. This result validates the TCA design, which takes advantage of the full opening of the vacuum interrupter.

Figure 48 shows that most measurements travel between 10% and 90% of the stroke in below 3.11 ms, and about 85% of the measurements achieve a separation of at least 7.5mm in less than 2.85ms. This performance validates the suitability of this actuator for the 14kV circuit breaker prototype to be developed in Task 3.8.

Figure 48: The histogram of the t_{10-90} and $t_{7.5}$ for 102 measurements.

6 Conclusions and Next Steps

The prototype of the MVDC circuit breaker started with the actuator, which will perform the contact separation for the vacuum interrupter. The system included a commercially available vacuum interrupter and a newly developed actuator, based on 3 disk Thomson Coil Actuator. The actuator prototype was developed in 2 stages: first prototype with 1 opening coil which was used to test the initial design, and the final prototype with all the three coils, which was built and tested to be validated for the circuit breaker prototype. The tests have shown that the developed TCA is suitable for the targeted application and has a stable operation. As next steps, the power electronics blocks for the circuit breaker prototype will be built, taking into account the requirements for the triggering of the actuator. As the TCA prototype for HYPERRIDE has achieved only TRL4 (testing in the laboratory), additional steps are needed to improve the manufacturability, including material selection for the mechanical stress that is developed in this actuator.

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